

Examining the Role of the Marketing Mix in Shaping Tourist Satisfaction: Evidence from Emerging Tourism Markets

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Abstract: Despite the importance of the tourism sector and its contribution to the growth of many national economies, this sector still faces several challenges in Africa. Especially, there is a clear deficiency in the effective use of marketing mix elements, which has negatively impacted the ability to attain tourist satisfaction. Therefore, this study aims to examine the effect of the marketing mix on tourist satisfaction. A quantitative approach using a cross-sectional method was adopted. To achieve the study objectives, a structured questionnaire was utilized for data collection. The questionnaire was distributed to both domestic and international tourists dealing with Kevalay and Afaq Misrata companies. A total of 397 respondents participated, selected through a convenience sampling technique. The data were analyzed using SEM. The findings revealed a significant and direct effect of the marketing mix on tourist satisfaction. The study includes theoretical and practical contributions, outlines key limitations, and provides valuable recommendations for future research.

Keywords: tourism marketing mix, tourist satisfaction, Emerging Tourism Markets, tourism sector in Libya, tourism sector in Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid economic developments witnessed globally have significantly contributed to the growth of many national economies. Among the most vital contributors to this economic advancement is the services sector, which plays a crucial role particularly in countries where other sectors, such as industry and agriculture, are underdeveloped, as well as in nations striving to diversify their economies (Al-Muhram et al, 2021; Al-Dmour, Al-Dmour, & Ahmadamin, 2023; Ateeq et al, 2024; Alshami et al, 2025). Within the broader service industry, the tourism sector has emerged as a key driver of economic growth, especially for countries seeking to expand their income sources and strengthen their competitiveness in the global market (Montañés-Del-Río & Medina-Garrido, 2020).

The tourism industry is currently undergoing rapid transformations, most notably characterized by an increasing reliance on modern technologies in marketing strategies and in enhancing the quality of services provided to tourists, and customer expectations has been increased. This shift is largely driven by heightened competition and rising customer expectations, necessitating that tourism enterprises adapt promptly to these changes to effectively meet the evolving needs of tourists (Al-Dmour, Al-Dmour, & Ahmadamin, 2023; Al-refaei et al, 2023; Ateeq et al, 2024).

However, Although the tourism sector in Libya has experienced significant growth, particularly in the period following 2011, several regions continue to face deficiencies in tourism-related infrastructure and accessibility. These shortcomings such as inadequate transportation networks, insufficient lodging options, and a lack of essential support services pose challenges for tourists attempting to reach specific destinations. Moreover, tourists often encounter restrictions in accessing tourism companies' operational spaces, which in turn negatively affects the overall satisfaction of tourists (Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025). Moreover, there is also a noticeable lack in the use and adaptation of marketing mix elements, which has negatively affected the ability of tourism companies to achieve positive tourist satisfaction (TS).

Tourism is widely recognized as relying heavily on the effectiveness of marketing tools in attracting tourists, achieving their satisfaction, building their loyalty (Mosiuk, 2021; Yudakova, 2021; Al-Adamat, 2023; Hawari, 2024). Marketing Mix (MM) is the high important factor that effect customer satisfaction, spicily in TS. Many studies confirming the effect of MM in truest; satisfaction such as Azhar et al (2019); Rahman et al (2019); Dethan et al (2020); Hawari (2024); Al-Dmour, Al-Dmour, and Ahmadamin (2023); Anggara, Sudiarta, & Arismayanti (2023). However, no more attention has been paid to the effect of MM on TS in Africa countries spicily on Libya, therefore, this study comes to fill this gap through investigation the effect of tourism MM on TS in tourism sector in Libya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between the MM and TS can be explained through Social Exchange Theory, which is based on the principle of "give and take" among different parties, whether individuals, groups, or organizations. According to this theory, relationships are viewed as reciprocal processes in which each party aims to maximize benefits while minimizing costs (Yamao, 2024; Sarmela, 2025). In the context of the interaction between tourists and tourism companies, the implementation of MM elements, namely product, promotion, process, and physical evidence, represents a form of both tangible and intangible exchange (Sarmela, 2025). Through these elements, tourism companies seek to meet tourist expectations and ensure their satisfaction in return for the money, time, and effort tourists invest (Poudel et al., 2021). When the perceived value of the MM exceeds tourists' expectations relative to what they have spent, satisfaction is likely to occur. Conversely, if the MM falls less than their expectations, tourists are more likely to experience dissatisfaction (al-refaei et al, 2024b).

The marketing mix (MM) is widely recognized as a key determinant of TS (Yuliviona et al, 2023; Watjanasoonorn, Viriyasuebphong, & Voraseyanont, 2019; Rahman et al., 2019). When tourism service providers effectively implement elements such as product quality, Promotion strategies, promotional efforts, and physical evidence, and processes (Yuliviona et al, 2023). visitors are more likely to feel satisfied with their overall experience. Tourist satisfaction (TS), in turn, is critical for building positive perceptions of a destination and enhancing its reputation. According to the scholars, satisfaction plays a central role in shaping future behaviors, including the likelihood of customer loyalty and revisiting a destination (Othman et al, 2019; Xie, 2020; Sarma, & Basumatary, 2023; Yuliviona et al, 2023; Hawari, Krisnatuti, & Asikin 2024). However, Tourist MM in this study included four elements:

Processes refer to the set of systems and activities carried out by a tourism institution to deliver or provide services to tourists. The procedures that a tourist undergoes during the service encounter including staff behavior and their interaction with customer play a critical role in shaping the overall tourist experience (Al-refaei et al, 2024). These processes should be implemented through well-organized, accurate, and error-free steps to ensure the service is delivered correctly from the outset. This contributes significantly to enhancing customer satisfaction with the destination (Mosiuk, 2021; Anggara, Sudiarta, & Arismayanti, 2023; Al-refaei et al, 2023; Hawari, Krisnatuti, & Asikin, 2024; Heydari, 2024; Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025). A positive initial impression not only influences the tourist's purchase decision but also serves as a foundational factor in determining their intention to revisit the destination in the future.

the product in tourist sector encompasses attractions, accommodations, transportation, and complementary services that form the complete visitor experience. Effective product development requires identifying and addressing the diverse needs of target segments, creating unique and memorable experiences (Kotler, Armstrong, & Balasubramanian, 2024; Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025). The tourism product is considered a broad and complex concept due to its dual nature, combining both tangible and intangible elements (Kotler et al, 2022). It is not merely a specific service or commodity, but rather an integrated set of services and components that collectively contribute to delivering a holistic experience for the tourist, that makes it subject to constant development in response to the evolving demands of the tourism market and customer expectations. In this regard, Kotler, Armstrong, and Balasubramanian (2024) emphasize that the tourism product is a combination of tangible and intangible elements offered in the market to effectively satisfy consumer needs.

The physical aspects of tourism institutions play an important role in shaping the image that tourists form in their minds and strongly influence their first impressions. These aspects help communicate the nature of the tourism facility and the quality of its services or products, especially to visitors who have not previously used them (Kotler, Armstrong, & Balasubramanian, 2024). Such physical cues are essential in giving tourists a sense of what to expect. They help create an early impression of the service or product quality and support visitors in forming realistic expectations before making a

decision to purchase or use the service (Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025). These physical elements may include a range of features such as parking areas, the main entrance, the design of doors and windows, the arrangement of furniture, the layout of tables and chairs, lighting systems, and the color of walls and ceilings (Sorokina et al, 2022). Moreover, the general atmosphere of the place also plays a role in shaping the visitors' satisfaction and overall opinion of the tourism institutions (Cempena, Brahmasari, & Suryani, 2019; Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025).

Tourism promotion is one of the most important and visible elements of the MM in the tourism sector. It includes a range of activities aimed at informing tourists about the tourism product, its features, and its benefits. It also plays a key role in influencing TS decisions and encouraging them to visit specific destinations (Murtini, Sutedjo, & Ibrahim 2023). Tourism promotion refers to both direct and indirect efforts carried out as part of the overall marketing strategy of a tourism organization or destination (Kotler, Armstrong, & Balasubramanian, 2024). The goal of this strategy is to increase tourist demand by using the most suitable promotional tools, depending on the nature of the product and the target market (Xiangyu et al, 2022). In addition, tourism promotion helps introduce the tourist to the product's characteristics by providing accurate and reliable information (Cai, Xu, Lu, & Lu, 2023). This process contributes to building a positive customer perspective of the destination, which can improve TS (Wahyudi & Yusra, 2021; Xiangyu et al, 2022; Cai, Xu, Lu, & Lu, 2023; Murtini, Sutedjo, & Ibrahim 2023; Rahayu, Nurahmi, & Samsuddin, 2023).

Despite many previous studies have been conducted regarding the effect of MM on TS in different countries with different culture and economics such as China, Indonesia, Jordan (e.g. Xie, 2020; Prihatin, Mus, Hasan, & Labbase, 2021; Xie et al, 2022; Anggara, Sudiarta, & Arismayanti, 2023; Al-Adamat et al, 2023; Yuliviona et al, 2023; Hawari, Krisnatuti, & Asikin, 2024; Wei, Tachateerapreda, & Panlopchanoknat, 2025), there is have not more attention of this relation on the Article, and pacifically in Libya, and cannot generalised the previous studies where the culture and economic is different (Al-refaei, 2019; Ghumiem, & Alawi, 2023; Alshuhumi et al, 2024; Ibrahim et al, 2024). Therefore, the current study comes to fill this gap through examine the effect of MM on TS in Libya.

3. METHODS

This study adopts a quantitative descriptive approach, which is highly appropriate for the nature of the research and its objectives, particularly in examining the impact of the MM on TS in KeValay Tourism Company and Afaq Misrata Tourism Company in Libya. The study sample consisted of 397 tourists, selected using the convenience sampling method from the target population.

Due to the unavailability of a list of the target population, it was not possible to use a probability sampling method. Consequently, the researcher was compelled to adopt a non-probability sampling approach (Saunders et al., 2019). Therefore, convenience sampling is widely used in social sciences and market research due to its practical advantages, and it is also considered a common and effective technique in studies related to customer satisfaction and loyalty (Adeiza et al., 2022). This method involves selecting participants who are easily accessible or readily available (Saunders et al., 2019). However, In this study, the questionnaire was distributed face-to-face to tourists at the sites of both Kevalay and Afaq Misrata tourism companies in Libya. This approach allowed the researcher to clarify any ambiguities in the questionnaire items and encouraged participation after reassuring respondents that their responses would remain confidential and used solely for research purposes.

Measurement

To measure the variables of this study (MM and TS). the researcher developed two customized instruments based on a comprehensive review of the relevant theoretical literature and previous empirical studies. In developing the MM scale, prior studies such as Dethan, Suryawardani, & Wiranatha(2020), were reviewed. The final scale consisted of 16 items distributed equally across four dimensions: physical evidence, promotion, process, and tourism product. Similarly, the tourist satisfaction (TS) scale was developed with reference to key studies including Rahman et al (2019), El-Manhaly (2024). This instrument also comprised 16 items covering four dimensions: satisfaction with staff, pricing, service diversity, and procedures. A five-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). For further details regarding the questionnaire items, see the appendix.

4. RESULTS

Sample profile description

The sample of this research included tourist from tourist sector in Libya, descriptive analysis shown that, 67.7 % were male and 32.3 were female. in terms of age, participants categorized into four age groups. Participants aged 31 to 40 years constituted the largest group at 31.0%, followed by those aged 41 to 50 years at 27.0%. Respondents aged 20 to 30 years accounted for 21.9%, while those aged over 50 years made up 20.1%. Regarding educational qualifications, the majority of participants held a high school diploma or equivalent, representing 49.6%. Participants with a bachelor’s degree formed 26.2%, followed by those with less than a high school education at 16.1%. A smaller proportion of the sample held master’s degrees 5.3%, and doctoral degrees 2.8%.

Evaluation of Measurement model

The evaluation of the measurement model, which included the constructs of MM and TS, generated satisfactory outcomes. The model fit indices indicated an acceptable fit to the data, with the following values: $\chi^2 = 1276.123$, degrees of freedom (df) = 455, CMIN/DF = 2.80, p-value < 0.000, CFI = 0.930, TLI = 0.924, and RMSEA = 0.068. These indicators suggest that the model demonstrated a strong overall fit (Alshuhumi et al, 2025).

Further examination of the measurement properties revealed robust internal consistency and construct validity. All standardized factor loadings surpassed the acceptable threshold of 0.50, with values ranging from 0.84 to 0.88 across all items. The CR for each construct was above the recommended level of 0.70, specifically 0.842 for MM, 0.876 for TS (Alsamawi et al., 2019). Additionally, the AVE for each construct exceeded the 0.50 benchmark, aligning with recommendations from Fornell and Larcker (1981) and further supported by recent studies (Alsamawi et al., 2019; Zumrah et al., 2021; Nasser et al., 2024).

Discriminant validity of the model was evaluated by comparing the square of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for for each variable with the inter-construct correlation estimates. According to Collier (2020), the square of the AVE for a given construct should exceed its correlations with all other constructs. In this model, the square of the AVE for each variable (highlighted in bold) is greater than its corresponding inter-construct correlations, confirming adequate discriminant validity. Table 22.4 presents the square root values of the AVE alongside the correlation coefficients among the model’s constructs.

Table 1. Reliability and validity of all variables

Construct	CR	AVE	MM	TS
Marketing Mix (MM)	0.842	0.572	0.756	-
TS (TS)	0.876	0.642	0.452***	0.801

The SEM of this study revealed significant direct effect of the MM on TS. The results supported this hypothesis, revealing a positive relationship between the MM and TS. The t-statistic for this relationship was 6.55, which exceeds the recommended threshold of 1.96 for statistical significance (Byrne, 2016; Muaydh et al, 2024). This indicates a strong and positive effect of MM on TS. Additionally, the p-value was 0.000, which is below the conventional significance level of 0.05, further confirming the statistical significance of the relationship (Ateeq et al, 2024). The path coefficient was 0.42, supporting the presence of a substantial positive influence of the MM on TS. These findings affirm the hypothesis and demonstrate a significant direct effect within the context of Kevala and Afaq Misrata Tourism Companies in Libya. Table 24.4 presents the detailed results of this hypothesis test.

Table 2. Standardized regression estimation of direct effects

Path	Standardized	t-Value	P-Value	Result
Marketing Mix → Tourist satisfaction	0.242	3.342	0.000	Supported

5. DISCUSSION

The study proposed a statistically significant direct effect of the MM on TS in Libya. The results supported this hypothesis, revealing a positive relationship between the MM and TS. When tourist companies provided effective implementation of key MM elements such as promotional strategies, physical evidence, tourism product, and operational processes by tourism service providers significantly contributes to enhancing tourists' overall experience and satisfaction. This elevated level of satisfaction plays a vital role in shaping positive perceptions of the destination and strengthening its overall reputation.

The implementation of MM elements such as product offerings, promotional strategies, service processes, and physical evidence serves as a mechanism through which tourism companies deliver value to tourists. These elements collectively contribute to forming the overall TS. When tourists perceive that the value they receive measured in terms of quality, service, and overall experience exceeds the costs they incur (including time, money, and effort), they are more likely to feel satisfied (Al-refaei et al, 2021). On the other hand, if the delivered experience does not meet or exceed their expectations, dissatisfaction may result. Therefore, the positive association found in this study between the MM and TS is consistent with the theoretical framework of Social Exchange Theory, as it highlights the importance of perceived value and mutual benefit in shaping favorable tourist perceptions.

Theoretical contribution

This study contributes to the literature by investigate the effect of MM on TS in different context that has different culture and economic such as Libya. The finding revealed that the MM has a positive and significant effect on TS can be interpreted through the lens of Social Exchange Theory. This theory emphasizes reciprocal interactions between individuals and organizations, where each party seeks to maximize benefits and minimize costs (Al-refaei, et al, 2019; Yamao, 2024; Sarmela, 2025). In the context of tourism, the relationship between tourists and tourism companies is shaped by the exchange of values. the implementation of MM elements, namely product, promotion, process, and physical evidence, represents a form of both tangible and intangible exchange (Sarmela, 2025). Through these elements, tourism companies seek to meet tourist expectations and ensure their satisfaction in return for the money, time, and effort tourists invest (Poudel et al., 2021).

Practical Implication

This study provides practical insights for tourism companies in Africa, particularly those operating within a sector that is currently in a phase of recovery and growth such as tourism sector in Libya. The findings highlight the critical role of the MM elements such as physical evidence, offerings, place, and operations in shaping TS with tourism establishments in Libya. Accordingly, it is essential for tourism organizations to pay close attention to all components of the MM and to continuously develop and improve them in order to enhance tourists' perceptions of both individual institutions and the Libyan tourism sector as a whole. In addition, the results of this study offer valuable guidance to tourism managers and practitioners, highlighting that focusing on tourists' needs and striving to meet or exceed their expectations through a well-structured MM can significantly enhance TS. In turn, this satisfaction contributes to strengthening the competitive position of tourism establishments in both local and regional markets.

Limitation

the current research is not without certain limitations that may affect the generalizability of its findings or its ability to fully capture all dimensions of the topic. The study primarily focused on analyzing the direct effect of the MM on TS within the Libyan tourism sector. In light of this, the researcher acknowledges several limitations that could serve as a foundation for future research or represent research gaps requiring further investigation.

For instance, future studies could explore all dimensions of the tourism MM in a more comprehensive manner and include a broader range of tourism companies. This is particularly important given that each company may differ in terms of its MM strategy and the quality of its services. Additionally, this study encourages future studies to examining other variables such as tourist trust, loyalty, intention to revisit destinations, the role of e-marketing, and the use of smart applications in booking and other service processes.

Data Statement

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request

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